

COLLECTION OF CROP BY-PRODUCT: EXPERIENCE ON WHEAT CHAFF

Luigi Pari¹, Simone Bergonzoli*², Negar Rezaei¹, Alessandro Suardi¹, Vincenzo Alfano¹, Nadia Palmieri¹, Walter Stefanoni¹, Paolo Mattei¹

Council for Agricultural Research and Economics, Research Center for Engineering and Agro-Food Processing (CREA-IT)

¹ Via della Pascolare, 16. 00015 Monterotondo (Rome) – ITALY

² Via Milano 43. 24047 Treviglio (Bergamo) ITALY

*Corresponding author: Simone Bergonzoli, simone.bergonzoli@crea.gov.it.

ABSTRACT: Wheat is one of the most widespread crops worldwide because of its high yield and importance for food, chemical purposes and livestock feed. Some of the residues of this crops (wheat chaff) remain in the field after grain harvesting. In Europe, the only wheat chaff could provide an annual potential biomass of 54.8 Mt. Collecting such a biomass could be of interest for bioenergy production and could increase farmers' income. However, progress in harvest technology play a key role in order to turn untapped by-products into valuable feedstock. The research represents a study of the performance and the quality of the work of an innovative system (Harcob), developed for maize cob collection, during wheat chaff harvesting. Results highlighted that it was possible to harvest 0.67 t ha⁻¹ of chaff, without affecting the harvesting performance of the combine. The Harcob system resulted suitable to harvest such different and high potential crop by-products and may represents a solution for farmers investing in the bioenergy production chain. **Keywords:** agricultural residues, harvesting, wheat chaff

1 INTRODUCTION

Bioenergy plays a significant role in climate change mitigation [1], substituting the fossil fuel for energy production. Agricultural sector is one of the main supplier of biomass through specific plantations of bioenergy crops or by residue from cropland [2]. This component of crop is constituted by the non-edible plant part that is not collected and usually left in the field [3]. Considering the European Renewable Energy Directive (RED II, directive 2018/2001/EU), the advantages of using agricultural residues for energy production are, on the one hand, the non-need for additional land and the non-competition with the food industry, and on the other hand to make an untapped product with a disposal cost, into an economic advantage for farmers. Hence, bioenergy is a tool to improve the economic and environmental sustainability of agricultural sector. A potential source of biomass is represented by the residues of wheat, spelt (*Triticum* spp., L.), and maize (*Zea mays* L.) [4,5]. Indeed, the EU-28 produced yearly 152 Mt wheat and spelt, and chaff, a heterogeneous mixture of glumes, dust, short straw pieces, broken grain seeds, and weed seeds, represents a potential biomass of 38 Mt year⁻¹ [6]. Considering the lowest heating value of chaff of 15.1 MJ kg⁻¹ [7], and the removal rate of 0.33, for a stable soil balance [8], it is possible to estimate a theoretical energy availability of 191 PJ year⁻¹ [9]. It is important to reiterate that the impact on soil nutrient and organic matter, and consequently on the productivity levels should be considered in the planning of residues removal [10]. However, even if relationship between the amount of residue maintained on the soil and the soil organic matter (SOM) was found in previous studies [11,12] due to the low nutrient content in cobs and wheat chaff, their removal is considered unlikely to affect soil fertility [9]. Furthermore, turning residues into a valuable feedstock mainly depends on technological advances of harvesting techniques. In some European regions, there are no markets or convenience to collect and use chaff and cob residue, and the on-field spreading or on-field burning results the most common method to dispose them of, and this is environmental unsustainable [13].

A substantial impulse to use some agricultural residues

for bioenergy can be represented by Harcob, a new harvesting system, developed by the Italian company Agricinque of Racca group (Marene, CN, Italy). The system consists of a device to separate maize cob and from the other residues (leaves, stem, culm, etc.) and an additional tank (9 m³) for storing collected materials. The system is patented and already commercial, but it is not already well developed on using this machine to harvest wheat chaff. In Europe, there is currently no established practice to collect chaff during harvesting, even if there are already technologies developed for its baling together with straw, or separated as a bulk product [14]. However, a collection and removal of chaff represents an herbicide-free weed management technique, as chaff contains most of the harvested weed seeds. Chaff collection can prevent the weed seeds from entering the soil and reduce the spread of weed patches.

The purpose of the trial was: 1) to verify the possibility of using the same combine harvester to gather wheat chaff (although it was developed to harvest the maize cob) with a new configuration. This approach will foster the utilization of two untapped biomass simplify the harvesting and reducing its cost.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Field and equipment characteristics

The study was conducted in July 2019 in the Northern Italy at Revello (44.709920 N and 7.435711 E), Cuneo province, for the harvesting of maize cob and wheat chaff, respectively. The farm is oriented to dairy farming and has a biogas power plant of 250 kWe fed by cow manure and litter, and maize residues (cob and stalks).

The test was carried out using a modified axial-flow combine harvester (Axial-flow 7130; Case IH, Racine, WI, USA), capable of harvesting separately the maize grains and threshed cobs. The combine was equipped with a specific cob harvesting device, comprising a threshing and separation system, a dedicated cob tank and an unloading device.

The cob is stored till is unloaded with an innovative auger system ensuring no blocking problems and allowing the discharging of cob (as well as chaff) and grain at the same

time. The combine can still be used for only grain harvesting, by manually disconnecting the main drive belt. The test was performed in three blocks (replicates), belonging to the same field, of about 0.5 ha each.

Furthermore, before starting the wheat harvesting test the combine was modified as follow:

The maize sieve (41 mm) was changed according to the dimension of the wheat seeds (28 mm). The crushing elements (knife) of the beating cylinder were changed.

The modification must be intended as an adaptation of the harvesting system to the different crop.

2.2 Pre-harvesting

Pre-harvesting measurements were performed to determine plant characteristics, the total biomass available and the dry matter content in the different plant fractions (seeds, chaff and straw). The pre-harvesting activities were the following:

10 sample areas (1 m² each) randomly chosen, corresponding to 10 m² in total, were hand harvested. The sample plot was chosen far from the edges to avoid the overestimation due to the "edge effect". The plants from the sampling areas were collected as whole plants from the ground level.

Plants of each sample area were weighed directly in field using a precision scale.

Pre-harvesting data were necessary to determine the total potential biomass available, the amount of biomass losses due to cut height (stubble), and the harvesting losses when the harvesting stage was completed. Wheat ears of each sample area were bagged and shipped to CREA institute in order to determine the single fractions using the laboratory thresher (Cicoria company, Thresher: PLOT 2375).

Three samples of grain, chaff and straw were randomly collected in each experimental field, weighed and stored into vacuum-packs to measure the moisture content. Biomass moisture content (MC) was determined according to ISO 18134-2:2017 [15]. The bulk densities (kg m⁻³) of the loose biomass of the cob/chaff stored in the Harcob tank was assessed taking 10 samples randomly selected and was measured according to ISO 17828:2015 [16]. The biomass remaining in the stubble was assessed measuring the average cut height that was evaluated by measuring 100 random cut heights transversally to the field for each block.

2.3 Work time study

The working time study was performed according to the CIOSTA (Comité International d'Organisation Scientifique du Travail en Agriculture) methodology and the recommendations from the Italian Society of Agricultural Engineering (A.I.I.A.) 3A R1 [17,18]. Harvested area were measured as well as the machines operation time, and yield obtained per each experimental field during the harvesting tests in order to calculate the theoretical field capacity (TFC, ha h⁻¹), the effective field capacity (EFC, ha h⁻¹) of the equipment used and their field efficiency (FE, %), and material capacity (MC, Mg h⁻¹).

The field capacity corresponds to the number of hectares that can be harvested per hour and its measurement is used to schedule field operations, labor, power units, and to assess machine operating costs. The effective field capacity (EFC) of a machine in the field was calculated by dividing the hectare completed by the hours of actual field time. TFC depends only on the full

operating width of the machine and the average travel speed in the field representing the maximum possible FC that can be obtained at the given field speed and full operating width of the machine is being utilized. EFC is less than TFC as a result of the various delays that may occur in the field during the work. The ratio of EFC to TFC represent the machine's FE.

FE is expressed as the percentage of a machine's TFC actually achieved under real conditions. It accounts for overlapping (failure to utilize the full operating width of the machine) and many other time delays like emptying grain and residues, traveling, turning, refilling the fuel tank, making adjustments, waiting for trucks and stops for the operator to rest. Other idle times due to activities that occur outside the field, such as travel to and from the field, major repairs or daily service, are not included in FE measurement. The MC of harvesting machines is often measured by the quantity of material harvested per hour (t h⁻¹). It is obtained multiplying the machine's EFC and the average yield of crop per hectare. Fuel consumption was recorded by using the measuring system of the combine harvester. Grain and residues of wheat were harvested per each block and weighed separately in the farm scale by using different trailers. After wheat straw baling, the bales produced from each experimental block were weighed.

The biomass losses were measured by knowing the total biomass available in the field (assessed during the pre-harvesting stage), the biomass left in the field due to the cut height (assessed during post-harvesting stage) and the grain and by-product harvested and baled.

$$\text{Harvesting losses (t ha}^{-1}\text{)} = \text{Rph} - \text{Se} - \text{St} - \text{B} - \text{T}$$

Rph= Total amount of biomass assessed in pre-harvesting stage (t ha⁻¹);

Se= amount of seeds (t ha⁻¹);

St= stubble (t ha⁻¹) (wheat/maize stalks (t ha⁻¹) * cut height (w%));

B= amount of baled residue (t ha⁻¹);

T= amount of chaff collected (t ha⁻¹).

In this regard, the biomass losses of each fraction (grain, chaff, straw) was obtained by the difference between biomass available (identified with plot analysis) and residues effectively collected during the harvesting phase.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pre-harvesting test permitted to assess a total amount of biomass per hectare of 25.9 (±0.34) tons, of which 11.5 (±1.01) tons of grain and 2.48 (±0.11) tons of chaff. The amount of straw was estimated in 8.58 (±1.08) tons per hectare of which 3.38 (±0.48) tons of stubble that remained in the soil due to the cutting height of the machine. The average value of the straw moisture content was 23.0 % (±1.4). Grain and chaff moisture content were 12.4 % (±0.4). The average bulk density of the chaff resulted 42.88 kg m⁻³. The Harcob system was developed for harvesting corn cob. Although, given the growing interest that the agricultural, industrial and research sectors are having towards unused wheat residues, once the necessary modifications to be made to the combine already described had been identified, specific harvesting tests were conducted to verify the possibility of using the Harcob system also for the separate harvesting of cereal husks.

During the wheat harvesting tests the grain and chaff collected were 10.93 and 0.67 t ha⁻¹, respectively. The material capacity was 12.98 t h⁻¹ and 0.79 t h⁻¹ for grain and chaff, respectively. Performance test results are summarized in Table I.

Table I: Results of the Wheat grain and chaff harvesting test with combine harvester CASE IH 7140 and Harcob system.

Parameters	Mean	Dev. St.
Theor. Field Capacity (ha h ⁻¹)	1.42	±0.05
Eff. Field Capacity (ha h ⁻¹)	1.19	±0.01
Yield (t seeds ha ⁻¹)	10.93	±0.43
Material capacity (t seeds h ⁻¹)	12.98	±0.66
Yield (t chaff ha ⁻¹)	0.67	±0.02
Material capacity (t chaff h ⁻¹)	0.79	±0.02
Fuel consumption (l ha ⁻¹)	29.86	±0.31

Results of pre-harvesting and harvesting tests were elaborated in order to define the mass balance and to assess the biomass losses. Harvesting tests carried out on wheat have shown the Harcob system's incapability of effectively separating the wheat chaff from the straw. In particular, the Harcob tank contained about 10 % of straw mixed with chaff. Furthermore, the windrow of residues generated by the combine was made by 50 % of chaff and 50 % of straw. Due to the results of the harvesting and the impossibility to distinguish chaff from straw, these two biomasses were considered together for the mass balance definition reported in Table II. Results highlighted 4.87 % of grain losses and 47.06 % of chaff and straw losses (excluding the stubble part that remained uncollected in the soil).

Table II: Wheat grain and residues losses assessment

Wheat fractions	Potential biomass* (tdw ha ⁻¹)	Harvested products (tdw ha ⁻¹)	Biomass losses (%)
Grain	10.2	9.7	4.87
Chaff	2.2	0.6	47.06
Straw	5.2	3.3	
Stubble	2.1	2.1	-
Total residues	9.5	6.0	47.06

Harcob system represents an innovation considering the possibility to perform a single-pass grain and cob harvesting with simultaneous unloading of the products (grain and cob), in two different trailers without affect the harvesting performance of the combine, and without modifying the harvesting method and costs. Harvesting tests were carried out to collect wheat chaff even if first results highlighted the need for further improvement and modifications due to high losses and the level of impurities measured. Harcob system was developed to be mounted in axial combine harvesters that can provide lower grain breakage percentage and higher productivity respect to the traditional harvesters with straw walkers but, on the other hand have stronger mechanical action on the straw. Even if Harcob system allows to collect 0.6 t ha⁻¹ of chaff for bioenergy, the use of Harcob showed 47 % of biomass losses. The amount of biomass losses could be explained by the straw crushing caused by the threshing system of the axial harvester. In fact, once the straw is cut in smaller parts, then the cleaning and ventilation system is not able to discriminate and separate the grain from the chaff and

from the straw. The result was that part of the chaff gone into the straw windrow.

Even if experiences of chaff harvesting are almost absent in bibliography, there are already machines on the market developed for the separate collection of chaff and straw, mainly to avoid the spread of weed seeds, but also for their use in animal husbandry or for the production of biofuel and energy [19,20]. The experience carried out by Pari (2018) [14] during chaff and straw collection by means a residue spreader tested in Sweden for chaff and straw baling, showed a residue harvesting losses between 31% to 47% [21]. This is to clarify that the harvesting efficiency of the Harcob system was similar to that of a system developed for the spreading of residues and that can partially, by changing the setting, allow a certain admixing of the chaff with the straw. For this reason, improvements will be necessary to optimize chaff harvesting with Harcob, reducing both product losses and increasing the separation capacity of the two fractions.

The risk of high bioenergies demand is the impacts of the Indirect land use change (ILUC which may occur when grazing land or farmland previously devoted to food production is turned over to the production of biofuels. This production change may expand agriculture land into areas with high carbon stock (i.e. peatlands, forests and wetlands), causing the release of greenhouse gases (CO₂ stored in soil and trees) and negating the benefits of using biofuels instead of fossil fuels, in terms of emission savings. Hence, the European Renewable Energy Directive (RED II) faces this risk. Consequently, alternative feedstock to produce bioenergies, as cobs and chaff, are fundamental to sustain the agro-energy production chain.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Wheat chaff is often an untapped residue less expensive compared dedicated energy crops. In fact, cereal chaff is a co-product of grain production, and excluding harvest and nutrient replacement, no additional costs are necessary. However, the feasibility of using this feedstock for bioenergy mainly is related to harvest methods used and biomass available and collectable per hectare. The scope of this research was to evaluate the operating parameters of the Harcob system and the quality and effectiveness of its work during wheat chaff through the innovative system (although it was developed to harvest the maize cob). According to the methodology utilized in this study it was possible to harvest 0.67 t ha⁻¹ of chaff. Although, the separate collection of the product, the increase in collection efficiency, and the presence of a specific market (for agricultural or industrial use) could make the use of by-product collection systems such as Harcob increasingly economically attractive.

In conclusion, the Harcob system could be considered suitable to harvest such high potential crop by-product and may represents a solution for farmers investing in the bioenergies production chains. Furthermore, the possibility of using the same combine harvester for two different cash crops in two different seasons will increase the profitability of the machine. Aspects related to the improvement of the system for chaff harvesting should be investigated and included in future studies.

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